

GUIDELINES FOR AUTHORS

The *Journal of Paper Conservation* is an international scholarly journal that aims to bring together scholarship and contributions to knowledge related to new research outcomes, innovative developments, and practice in the preservation and conservation of cultural heritage objects of archives, libraries, and graphic art collections. The journal seeks to be a central forum for sharing knowledge on conservation policies, conservation treatments, ethical issues, and the history of the book, paper, and related materials. It includes several types of articles ranging from the most theoretical to the most practical aspects of book and paper conservation in order to offer everyone the possibility to share experiences. The target groups are paper, book, and photograph conservators, book and paper historians, photography historians, art historians, archivists, librarians, and conservation scientists.

TYPES OF CONTRIBUTIONS

Articles

Research article (peer-reviewed)

These are scholarly articles of academic level focusing on innovative research work that contributes knowledge to the field of conservation.

Projects / In Practice / Professional Matter

Articles of this type deal with current or past conservation or preservation projects, professional matters, and hands-on conservation, reflecting on the practical aspects of the field.

Special Sections

Degree work

Summaries of degree works recently awarded in the paper and book conservation field are included here.

Instructables

Instructables describe specific techniques, technical tips, and conservation know-how (complete with step-by-step photographs or illustrations, brief explanations, and materials used).

Materials & Equipment

This section introduces in short specific materials or equipment that proved to be useful to conservators.

Book reviews

Reviews of significant publications from disciplines of interest to the readership of JPC are assigned by the Editorial Board. Unsolicited reviews will not be considered. Reviews should be fair to the author and to the work. Authors who wish to write a review should email to jpc.submission@iada-home.org.

SUBMISSION

Authors should submit their articles as attached documents via email to the Journal's submission email address: jpc.submission@iada-home.org. Articles are submitted in the English language. Please use British English spelling consistently throughout your manuscript. Submissions in other languages are also welcome, but these will be translated into English for publication by IADA in collaboration with the Editor and the Author(s). The manuscript should follow the style guidelines found at <http://bit.ly/JPC-Guidelines>. Articles should be submitted with a covering email clearly stating the name, address and affiliation of the corresponding author, as well as the intended type of contribution.

FROM EDITION TO PUBLICATION

After submission, the corresponding author will be contacted by a JPC editor who will inform him about deadlines, peer-review, and the following steps. The article may undergo final language editing once the corresponding author

and the editor agree on a close to final version. The final article is then sent to the publisher. The publisher does the layout of the article and forwards the page proofs to the corresponding author for final corrections and approval. Only minor corrections are possible at this stage. The author should carefully read the proof in order to pick up editing errors (usually stylistic or typing errors).

Authors who will be away from their offices during the process (for instance during summer holidays) should inform the editor and the publisher.

PRIOR AND SIMULTANEOUS PUBLICATION

The journal aims to publish original articles dealing with the broad field of the preservation and conservation of cultural heritage on paper and related materials. Articles are accepted for consideration by JPC with the understanding that they represent original material, have not been published previously, are not being considered for publication elsewhere, and have been approved by each author. The article (and illustrations) must be free of copyrights held by third parties. Authors should inform the editor when submitting articles containing content previously published, used in publications that are in press, submitted for publication, or soon to be submitted. If in doubt, please do not hesitate to contact us.

SUPPLEMENTAL ONLINE MATERIALS

The journal accepts supplementary material, such as video and sound files, datasets, filesets, 3D models, or anything which supports (and is pertinent to) your paper. These will be published alongside the online version via Figshare on Taylor and Francis's website. See

<<https://authorservices.taylorandfrancis.com/publishing-your-research/writing-your-paper/enhance-article-with-supplemental-material/>>

ARTICLE STRUCTURE AND FORMAT

Article structure

For both Research Articles and Projects, please make sure that your manuscript contains the following parts and information (in this order) (* if applicable):

- Title
 - Abstract
 - Keywords
 - Main text
(including low resolution figures and tables)
 - Faculty advisor(s)*
(for Degree works only)
 - Acknowledgements*
 - Appendices*
 - Notes*
 - Figure permissions*
 - References / Bibliography
 - Suppliers list*
- For anonymity in the reviewing process, please provide the following information in your cover email only, or in a separate file, and not directly written in the paper's manuscript:
- Full name(s) of author(s) in correct order
(corresponding author indicated with *)
 - Author(s) affiliation(s)
 - Author(s) ORCID iD*
 - Corresponding Author(s) contact details
 - Author(s) short biography

Title

Please, provide a concise title, in a one or two-part format.

Abstract

The abstract should not exceed 150 words. Please do not include any references or figures. A German translation of the abstract will be provided by JPC editors or by the author (if native German speaker) and is included following the English version.

Keywords

Three to five keyword terms should be provided to help find your article with searching tools. A German translation will be provided by JPC editors or the author (if native German speaker).

Main text

Authors are recommended to structure their papers well. A typical submission would follow a structure similar to the following (* indicates sections conventionally used in papers of a more scientific content):

- 1) Introduction
(including description of problem)
- 2) Background information and Literature review
(background with references, objectives and research questions)
- 3) Main contribution | Experimental information (materials, methods)*
- 4) Results*
- 5) Discussion
- 6) Conclusions

If necessary (1) and (2) can be combined in one section; as well as (4) and (5). When describing a conservation research project, one may take some liberty with this content and include a conservation report section, or a conservation treatment section.

Word count

Typical Research Articles are between 6,000 to 10,000 words in length. Projects Papers usually run between 3,000 to 5,000 words.

Faculty advisor(s)

Please, for Degree work contributions, provide the name of the supervisor(s).

Acknowledgements

Disclosure of financial relationships is required. Financial support for the study is always disclosed, whether from governmental, non-profit, or commercial sources. Please supply all details required by your funding and grant-awarding bodies as follows:

- For single agency grants:
This work was supported by the <Funding Agency> under Grant <number xxx>.
- For multiple agency grants:
This work was supported by the <Funding Agency #1> under Grant <number xxx>; <Funding Agency #2> under Grant <number xxx>; and <Funding Agency #3> under Grant <number xxx>.

Nonfinancial forms of support, such as analytic support, or other assistance with preparation of the article, must also be acknowledged. However, substantial contributions to the paper and the work described should be indicated as co-authorship, and not as an acknowledgement.

The background of the study (diploma work, PhD, Postdoctoral work, etc.) should be mentioned as well as any presentations at meetings, etc. Acknowledgements may include dedications.

Appendices

Detailed information that would be distracting in the main body of the paper, and are too substantial to be used as note material, should be included in an appendix (or series of appendices). Examples of items that might be in an appendix include lists of items, questionnaires, detailed descriptions of tools used in the research, etc. If a paper only has one appendix, this should be labeled *Appendix*; if there is more than one appendix, these should be labeled with Roman numerals (*Appendix I*, *Appendix II*, etc.), in the order that each item appears in the paper. In the main text, appendices should be referred to by their labels.

Short biography

Please, provide a short biography (max 150 words) for each author.

Notes

Information that supplements the text, but that would be distracting or inappropriate to include in the body of the paper, should be included as endnotes. Notes should be used sparingly and made as concise as possible. If a note is

longer than a few sentences, please, consider whether this information should be incorporated into the main text instead, or, possibly, as an appendix. Straight bibliographical references go in parentheses in the main text, and not in a note. Notes can be automated in a word processor; please, use endnotes.

Figure permissions

Simple figure permissions should be incorporated in the figure captions. More complex statements and grouping of permissions can also be included in a dedicated section of the paper.

References

Authors should carefully inform the reader of ideas and works that influenced the paper.

"It is essential that you acknowledge your debt to the sources of data, research and ideas on which you have drawn by including references to, and full details of, these sources in your work" (Student Learning Development, University of Leicester 2009). Whenever possible, indicate also the page numbers of the reference.

JPC's style is based on the Harvard X referencing style. We created a stylesheet that you can download at <<http://bit.ly/JPC-BibRefStylesheet>> and add to your reference management software such as the open-source Zotero (www.zotero.org/download/).

Suppliers list

Please include a list of suppliers with their contact details for all the products mentioned in the text and their reference numbers.

In the cover email, or a separate file also include:

Name(s)

Please, provide the full name of all authors in the correct order. Indicate the corresponding author with *.

Affiliation(s)

Please, provide the affiliation(s) for all authors. Authors belonging to different affiliations should be matched with the correct one with a superscript letter, e.g., John Smith^a, Ada Lovelace^b || ^aNational Library, ^bNational Archives.

ORCID iD(s)

If available, please, provide the author(s) ORCID iD(s) <<https://orcid.org/>>.

Contact details

Include email address, postal address and website URL (if any) for the corresponding author only. If the corresponding author has no affiliation (e.g. independent scholar), only provide a postal address.

SPECIAL TYPES OF CONTRIBUTIONS: STRUCTURE AND FORMAT

Degree Work

Please make sure that the full text does not exceed 500 words (~3000 characters including spaces) and contains the following information (* if applicable):

- Title of the Diploma work
- Author's name
- Name of the university or school of conservation (as affiliation)
- ORCID iD*
- Author's contact details (name, address, phone, email)
- Abstract in English (50 words max). A German translation will be provided
- Keywords in English (3-5). A German translation will be provided
- Text
- Faculty advisor's name
- One figure and figure caption
- Suppliers' list*

Instructables

Please make sure that the text contains the following sections (* if applicable):

- Title
- Author's name
- Author's affiliation
- ORCID iD*
- Author's contact details (name, address, phone, email)
- Abstract in English (50 words max). A German translation will be provided
- Keywords in English (3-5). A German translation will be provided
- Introduction describing the context and the field of application of the proposed method
- Figures and captions
- List of material and tools necessary for the implementation of the practical know-how
- Notes*
- Suppliers list
- References*

Keep in mind that 'Instructables' should remain brief. Limit the number of figures to those absolutely essential and caption them concisely. The length of 'Instructables' is limited to 1 to 3 pages.

Materials & Equipment

Please make sure that the text contains the following sections (* if applicable):

- Title
- Author's name
- Author's affiliation
- ORCID iD*
- Author's contact details (name, address, phone, email)
- Abstract in English (50 words max). A German translation will be provided
- Keywords in English (3-5). A German translation will be provided
- Introduction presenting the equipment, how to use it, and why it is useful
- Figures and captions
- Supplier of the material
- References*

The length of a Materials & Equipment submission is limited to 1 page. Note that this section is not dedicated to publicity but to objective reports of practical experience.

Book Reviews

Please make sure that the text contains the following sections (* if applicable):

- Title: Full bibliography reference of book under review, complete with number of pages, price, and ISBN:
Brandi, C. 2005. *Theory of Restoration*. Firenze: Nardini editore; Istituto Italiano per il Restauro, 186 pp. €23,00. ISBN: 978-88-404-4089-5
- Review Author's name
- Review Author's affiliation
- Review Author ORCID iD*
- Review Author's contact details (name, address, phone, email)
- Review text (see below for details)

Reviews of significant publications from disciplines of interest to the readership of JPC are assigned by the Editorial Board. Unsolicited reviews will not be considered. The length of a review submission should be between 1,000 to 1,500 words. Deadlines are usually three months from the date of assignment. Reviews should be fair to the author and to the work. Although the content of reviews does not represent the judgments of the Editors, the Editors reserve the right to reject reviews that do not meet the expected criteria and standards of professionalism, intellectual rigor, and impartiality.

An acceptable review must provide a clear description of the content of the book and of the author's method and purpose. Building on that foundation, a reviewer should offer fair critical judgment of the book's strengths and weaknesses and should aspire to assess the importance of the book in the context of other scholarship. Footnotes, charts, illustrations, and long lists of errata are rarely appropriate in a review.

The reviewer of a book in JPC should not review the same book elsewhere. Authors who wish to write a review should email to jpc.submission@iada-home.org.

STYLE, FORMATTING, AND REFERENCING

General structure of the Text

The text should be divided into logical sections, denoted by main heading levels. Please use the following formats to indicate different levels of headings in your main text:

- Main heading (2) **Experimental** (bold)
- Sub-heading (2.1) ***Material and Equipment*** (bold, italic)
- Sub-sub-heading (2.1.1) *Artificial ageing* (italic)

For consistency, and ease of use, it is advisable to assign text styles in the word processor of the author's choice.

Referencing WITHIN the Text

When presenting data as listed below, please include fully detailed information in the following style. References should always be referred to in your main text. Please check that your bibliography does not include an article that is not referred to in the text or omit an article that is referred to in the text.

Preferably, insert all citations at the end of a sentence.

JPC's referencing style is based on Harvard X. At this link at <<http://bit.ly/JPC-BibRefStylesheet>> authors can find a stylesheet that can be used within a reference management software such as the open-source Zotero (www.zotero.org/download/) to automatically style inline references and bibliography lists. Alternatively, use the following guidelines.

Institutes

Institutes can be mentioned in English or in their native language, but should be followed by their location (city, country). [...] research was carried out at the Library of Congress (Washington DC, USA), and the Rijksmuseum (Amsterdam, The Netherlands) [...]

Materials, equipment and analytical methods

These should be mentioned as (technical data, apparatus: supplier). [...] aged in a Xenon-test chamber (Xenochrome 320 filter system, spectral energy distribution 320–800 nm, Alpha High Energy-LM-W: Atlas MTT GmbH) [...] [...] Methylcellulose (MC 3000: Aqualon) [...]

If technical data or specification details are not available, the supplier should be mentioned. [...] on the suction table (Belo Restaurierungsgeräte GmbH) [...]

Bibliographic references

Literature citations should include the author's name and the year of publication as (author,1 year). Volatile degradation products were analysed (Schwarz, 1998).

Reference to the page number can be done as (author1, year: page[–range]). According to previous work it can be assumed that [...] (Schwarzkopf, 1999: 35–36).

Two authors should be referred to as (author1 & author2, year). It was demonstrated that [...] (Schweidler & Johnson, 1975).

Three and more authors should be referred to as (author1 *et al.*, year). Previous work (Müller *et al.*, 1999: 15) showed that [...]

When two publications of the same author are cited together, there is no need to repeat the author's name. Two or more publications cited in the text by the same author, in the same year, should be listed with a, b, c. Some previous work was realized in this field (Strlic *et al.*, 2000a, 2000b, 2000c).

Several references cited together should be mentioned as (author1, year1; author2, year2; author3, year3,

year3).

These aspects were already investigated (Durand *et al.*, 1999; Smith, 2001; Jackson & Suki, 2000; Müller *et al.*, 1999, 2000).

If the name of the author appears in the main text before the citation, use the name also in the citation as 'author (author, year).

As investigated by Durand (Durand *et al.*, 1999).

Personal communications

Personal communications are not considered to be literature references, but can be cited in the text in the following manner: Name ([employer], [city, country], year, personal communication, [day] [month])

"Heinz Friedrich (Stadtmuseum, Essen, Germany, 2001, personal communication, 21 October)."

Standards

Standards are considered to be bibliographic references. The standard institute (ISO, ASTM, NF, etc.) should be cited with the reference number and year of publication as (institute number: year)

These measurements were performed according to a standard process (ISO 105-B02: 1978).

Web sites

Web pages are considered bibliographic references and should be cited as monographs (Author, date). Several pages from the same site can be listed with the Year-letter system (Author, datea, date, datec).

The 'prognosis' routine (National Archives, 2012a) was implemented [...] the phytate solution was prepared following a protocol currently in use in the paper community (National Archives, 2012b).

Quotations

Please use single quotation marks, except where 'a quotation is "within" a quotation'. Please note that long quotations should be indented without quotation marks.

Measuring units

Please use units as stated in the International System of Units (SI) (non-italicized). Other very common units are also accepted as follows:

L	litre (use 'L' instead of 'l')
mL, µL	millilitres, microliters
°C	degrees Celsius
m, cm, mm, µm	metres, centimetres, millimetres, micrometres
min, h	minutes, hours
g, mg, µg	grams, milligrams, micrograms
ppm	parts per million

Use scientific notation if several units are to be linked. A linkage of units is indicated by a centred dot '·' not an 'x'.

A paper weight is expressed in g·m⁻² (not in g/m²)
A concentration should be expressed in g·L⁻¹ or mol·L⁻¹ (not in g/L or in mol/L)

Fractions should be expressed in scientific notation; do not use a slash '/'.

TABLES AND FIGURES

Please limit the use of figures to those that are necessary for your article. Make sure that the preferred position of your figures within your text is clearly indicated by either inserting (low resolution!) images, diagrams or tables at

the respective position or use blank squares as a replacement. You should be aware that positional changes in the final layout may be unavoidable, due to the restrictions of a two-column layout.

Tables

Tables should present new information rather than duplicating what is in the text. Readers should be able to interpret the table without reference to the text. Please supply editable files.

Figures

All figures must additionally be submitted separately as highly resolved image files in TIFF or JPG format (avoid high compression rates of JPG files). Label your image files clearly by indicating the author's name and number of the figure in the text (e.g. Martin_Fig_02.jpg).

Your image files should provide a resolution of **600 dpi for grayscale and 300 dpi for colour** in the final image size, with an aspect ratio of **4:3**. For images to fit in 1 column, the horizontal dimension should be 7.4 cm and 15.9 cm when spanning across 2 columns.

Diagrams or graphs embedded in a Word document should also be provided separately either in their original file format (e.g. as Excel file.xls) or be converted into a high-resolution image file format (TIFF or JPG with **1200 dpi**). **Be aware that drawings generated with MS Office tools are not suitable for printing.**

Only figures that are **free of copyrights** of other parties can be published. It is by default assumed that photographs are taken by the main author. If this is not the case, the author should indicate the copyright and make sure that the owner of the photograph agrees to its publication.

Please, limit the number of images to around 2 figures per page.

Equations

If you are submitting your manuscript as a Word document, please ensure that equations are editable.

Captions and referencing of figures

Each figure and table must be provided with a caption which names the table/figure number and a brief description of the depicted content (preferably only one or two sentences). The caption should be understandable without reference to the text.

Tables and figures have to be referred to in the main text respectively as (Table 1) or (Figure 1). They must be numbered in consecutive order of appearance in the text with Arabic numerals. It is possible to make use of automated numbering and cross-referencing offered by any word processing software.

LIST OF SUPPLIERS

Please include a list of suppliers of all the products and their reference numbers used in the study. Make sure that any material/equipment that is quoted in the text is also listed here.

Use the following structure: Name of supplier, address, country, Tel, web address (product 1, reference 1; product 2, reference 2, etc.)	Sigma Aldrich Chimie, 80 rue Luzais, 38 070 Saint Quentin Fallavier, France, Tel: +33 474 822 888, www.sigmaaldrich.com (gallic acid monohydrate, 398225; iron II sulphate heptahydrate, 215422; gum arabic, G9752)
--	--

The product reference number can be omitted when there is no risk of confusion.	Stouls, 9-11 rue de l'Orme Saint-Germain - 91165 Champlan Cedex, France, Tel: +33 1 69 101 070, www.stouls.com (Tylose MH300P; Reemay 17 g-m-2)
---	--

REFERENCES

JPC's style is based on the Harvard X referencing style. We created a stylesheet that you can download <<http://bit.ly/JPC-BibRefStylesheet>> and add to your reference management software such as the open-source Zotero (www.zotero.org/download/) to automatically style inline references and bibliography lists.

References should be listed **alphabetically by author** in the format given below.

Multiple publications cited by the same author should be listed chronologically. Several publications by one author in one year should be referred to as: (2009a, 2009b).

When inserting URLs for web pages and similar, preferably, refer to the page archived in the Internet Archive (<https://web.archive.org/>) as opposed to the direct link that might not be permanent. See Websites below.

Type	Examples
<i>Edited Books</i>	
Surname, initial of First Name, ed. (or eds.) Year. <i>Title in italic</i> , [edition]. Publisher city: Publisher. <i>[In Zotero select 'book' as the Item type; make sure to indicate correctly the editor(s) as such]</i>	Banik, G. and Weber, H.-M., eds. 1999. <i>Tintenfrassschäden und ihre Behandlung</i> . Stuttgart: Kohlhammer.
<i>Books</i>	
Surname, initial of First Name, Year. <i>Title in italic</i> , [edition]. Publisher city: Publisher. <i>[In Zotero select 'book' as the Item type]</i>	Zerdoun Bat-Yehouda, M. 2003. <i>Les encres noires au Moyen Âge jusqu'à 1600</i> . Paris: CNRS Éditions.
<i>Book Chapters</i>	
Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title of chapter. In: Initial of Editor, Surname of Editor, ed(s). <i>Title of book in italic</i> . Publisher City: Publisher, pp. first-last page. <i>[In Zotero select 'book section' as the Item type; make sure to indicate correctly the editor(s) and the author(s) as such]</i>	Krekel, C. 1999. Chemische Struktur historischer Eisengallustinten. In: G. Banik and H.-M. Weber, eds. <i>Tintenfrassschäden und ihre Behandlung</i> . Stuttgart: Kohlhammer, pp. 25–36.
<i>Journal Articles</i>	
Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. <i>Name of Journal in italic</i> , Volume(Issue):first-last page. [DOI]/[Accessed Date].[Available at: <URL>]. <i>[In Zotero select 'journal article' as the Item type]</i>	Clarkson, C. 2019. The Winchester Bible: Notable Features Observed During Conservation, 2012–15. <i>Journal of Paper Conservation</i> , 20(1–4):49–55. DOI: 10.1080/18680860.2019.1748963.
<i>Magazine Articles</i>	
Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. <i>Name of Journal in italic</i> , Volume(Issue):first-last page. [DOI]/[Accessed Date].[Available at: <URL>]. <i>[In Zotero select 'magazine article' as the Item type]</i>	Barber, G. 2016. X-Rays Are Revealing the Mysterious Writings in Mummy Coffins. <i>Wired</i> . [Accessed 17 Nov 2018]. Available at: < www.wired.com/2016/10/x-rays-revealing-mysterious-writings-mummy-coffins/ >.
<i>Newspaper Articles</i>	
Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. <i>Name of Newspaper in italic</i> , day month. [pp. first-last page]. [Accessed Date].[Available at: <URL>]. <i>[In Zotero select 'newspaper article' as the Item type]</i>	Edwards, A.S.G. 2013. Back to the Real: What Do We Lose When We Replace Access to Manuscripts with Digitisation? <i>Times Literary Supplement</i> , 7 Jun. [Accessed 3 Aug 2019]. Available at: < www.the-tls.co.uk/articles/private/back-to-the-real-2/ >

Conference Proceedings

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title of article. In: Initial of Editor, Surname of Editor, ed(s). *Title of the Proceedings in italic* (it is good practice to include the name and date of the conference). Location: Publisher, pp. first-last page.

[In Zotero select 'conference paper' as the Item type; make sure to indicate correctly the editor(s) and the author(s)]

Dictionary or Encyclopædia Entries (printed)

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title of entry. In: *Title of book in italic*. [Volume]. Publisher City: Publisher, pp. first-last page.

[In Zotero select 'book section' as the Item type]

Dictionary or Encyclopædia Entries (online)

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title of entry. [Edition]. *Title of dictionary in italic*. [Accessed Date].[Available at: <URL>].

[In Zotero select 'dictionary entry' as the Item type]

Websites

Name. Date. *Page title in italic*. [Accessed Date].[Available at: <URL>].

[In Zotero select 'web page' as the Item type]

Blog or Forum Posts

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title of post. *Title of blog or forum in italic*. [Accessed Date].[Available at: <URL>].

[In Zotero select 'blog post' as the Item type]

Original Artwork

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title of artwork. Medium. [Artwork size]. Archive/Gallery, Location, [call number].

[In Zotero select 'artwork' as the Item type]

Multimedia (audio, video, etc.)

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. Format. Publisher.

[In Zotero select 'audio recording' as the Item type, regardless of the format]

Presentations

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. Type. Meeting name, delivered Date. [Accessed Date]. Available at: <URL>.

[In Zotero select 'presentation' as the Item type]

Clarkson, C. 1980. Preservation and Display of Single Parchment Leaves and Fragments. In: G. Petherbridge, ed. *International Conference on the Conservation of Library and Archive Materials and the Graphic Arts, Cambridge, 22-26 September 1980. Abstracts and Preprints*. London: Society of Archivists; Institute of Paper Conservation, pp. 113–119.

Diderot, D. and D'Alembert, J. le R. 1772. Livre. In: *Encyclopédie Ou Dictionnaire Raisonné Des Sciences, Des Arts et Des Métiers*. Vol. 9. Paris: Briasson, pp. 601–621.

OED. 2010. 'conservation, n.' Third edition. *Oxford English Dictionary Online*. [Accessed 7 Dec 2020]. Available at: <<https://www.oed.com/view/Entry/39564>>.

IADA. 2017. *Journal of Paper Conservation*. [Accessed 7 Dec 2020]. Available at: <<https://web.archive.org/web/20171127132455/https://www.iada-home.org/en/journal-of-paperconservation/current-issue.html>>.

Smith, M.J. 2006. J. A. Szirmai. *Conservation DistList*. [Accessed 24 Oct 2018]. Available at: <<http://www.cool.conservation-us.org/byform/mailling-lists/cdl/2006/0666.html>>.

Bray, D. de. 1607. *Mensen en twee honden in een boekenwinkel (People and two dogs in a book shop)*. Pen and brown ink, brush in gray on paper. 222 x 222, (Inventory) Rijksmuseum Amsterdam, Rijksprentenkabinet, RP-T-1884-A-290.

Hill, R., Waters, P., and Clarkson, C. 1968. *The Restoration of Books, Florence, 1968: A Film Based on the Work in the National Library of Florence Resulting from the Floods on 4 November 1966*. Film. Royal College of Art funded by Italian Art Rescue Fund.

Turner, M. 1988. *Ten Years of Conservation in the Bodleian*. Lecture 256. Rare Books School, delivered 19 Apr. [Accessed 20 Feb 2020]. Available at: <<https://soundcloud.com/rarebookschool/turner-ten-years>>

Interviews

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. Format. Publisher.

[In Zotero select 'audio recording' as the Item type]

Zor, M. and Clarkson, C. 2008. *Interview with Christopher Clarkson*. Mp3. Ljubljana: National Radio of Slovenia. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3679147>.

Manuscripts, unpublished material

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. Type.

[In Zotero select 'manuscript' as the Item type]

Petersen, T.C. 1948. *Coptic bindings in the Pierpont Morgan Library*. Unpublished manuscript in the Pierpont Morgan Library.

Reports or online grey literature

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. Place: Institution, Report Number. [Accessed Date]. Available at: <URL>.

[In Zotero select 'manuscript' as the Item type]

Webster, G. 1964. *Romano-British Coarse Pottery: A Student's Guide*. York: Council for British Archaeology, No. 6. [Accessed 15 Dec 2011]. Available at: <http://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/catalogue/adsdata/arch-281-1/dissemination/pdf/cba_rr_006.pdf>.

Theses/Dissertations/Diploma Works

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Title. Type. School/University, City.

[In Zotero select 'thesis' as the Item type]

Hadgraft, N. 1998. English fifteenth century book structures. Ph. D. Thesis. University College London, London.

Standards

Standard Institution. Year. *Title in italic (insert the standard code here)*. Location: Institution.

[In Zotero select 'book' as the Item type]

ANSI/NISO/LBI. 2000. *ANSI/NISO Z39.78-2000 (R2010) Library Binding*. Bethesda (MD): NISO.

Statutes/Legislation

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. Name of Act. Code Number. Code Type.

[In Zotero select 'statute' as the Item type]

Ciampi, C.A. 2004. *D.lsg 42/2004: Codice dei beni culturali e del paesaggio, ai sensi dell'articolo 10 della legge 6 luglio 2002, n. 137*. Vol. 42. Decreto Legislativo.

Software

Surname, initial of First Name. Year. *Title in italic*. Location: Publisher. [DOI]/[Accessed Date]. Available at: <URL>.

[In Zotero select 'software' as the Item type]

Campagnolo, A. and Porter, D. 2014. *VisColl 1.0. Modeling and Visualizing Physical Manuscript Collation*. Philadelphia (PA): KislakCenter. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4300278>.

The Journal of Paper Conservation gathers bibliographic references cited in the papers published in an online Zotero library <<https://www.zotero.org/groups/2407780>>, with the hope that it may become a resource for conservators, and authors in general, looking for current and historical research articles in the fields of book and paper conservation, and related subjects, such as heritage science, art history, book history, paper history, archaeology of the book, photography conservation and history. Subsets of the database for specific projects or subjects are also published, for instance, the items mentioned in the examples can be found on a collection at: https://www.zotero.org/groups/2407780/journal_of_paper_conservation/collections/MTQP2MPE.